

UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' PERCEPTION OF BEING AN INTERNATIONAL STUDENT: A METAPHOR ANALYSIS STUDY

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to determine the perceptions of international students studying in Turkey and university students who are Turkish citizens and continue their education in Turkey in relation to being an international student with the help of metaphors. The study group consists of 79 students, 35 of which are Turkish citizens and 44 are international students, studying at Giresun University in the spring term of the 2016-2017 academic year. The study was conducted according to the phenomenology model among qualitative research patterns. The data of the study were obtained by university students filling in the sentences such as "being an international student is similar to/like..... because.....". The international students in the study group produced 43 different valid metaphors and students who were Turkish citizens produced 27 different valid metaphors. It was observed that 59 of these metaphors were positive, and 11 of them were negative. The metaphors created by the international students were included in 11 categories, and the metaphors created by the students who were Turkish citizens were included in nine categories.

Keywords: metaphor, metaphorical perception, international student

1. Introduction

Many students go to other countries than their own countries to receive higher education due to competition or quota limits, the lack of departments that require expertise or the effects of negative political and social factors in their countries (Arkali-

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Olcay and Nasır, 2016). Turkey has become an attractive country especially for students in the Turkish Republics and related communities because of its program diversity in higher education, the opening of additional quotas for foreign students in postgraduate and doctoral programs, and cultural affinity. The idea that the education in our country is more qualified and the fact that Turkey is perceived as a country worth living can be shown among the reasons why these students prefer Turkey in higher education (Kıroğlu, Kesten and Elma, 2010). In a study carried out by Tekelioğlu, Başer, Örtlek and Aydınli (2012), it was suggested that the large part of international students coming to Turkey prefer our country according to preliminary information and expectation. This situation shows that many students who come to Turkey for higher education consciously prefer Turkey. However, international students face education problems caused by being a student during their higher education as well as some socio-cultural problems such as being in a different country, cultural differences, difficulties in family longing and dormitory life, accommodation, health and incompatibility in friend relationships. Meeting these needs facilitates the adaptation process of international students (Uygun, 2004; Ghanbary, 2017).

In our country, the definition of "international student" has been used instead of the definition of "foreign student" in recent years, and the contribution that these students make to the "international" identity of the university is brought to the forefront despite the "other, different" meanings of the word "foreign" (Özkan and Acar-Güvendir, 2015). "A student who is not a citizen of the Republic of Turkey (R.T) and who is studying on his own account or on a scholarship for social, cultural and professional development in an educational institution of all grades and branches in Turkey with student visas or special permits" is defined as an international student (Ministry of Development, 2015). When the data of the Presidency of the Council of Higher Education on international students studying in Turkey are examined, it is observed that a total of 103.727 international students continued their education in our country in the 2016-2017 academic year. Among them, Azerbaijani citizens are ranked as the first with 15.036 people, Syrian citizens are ranked as the second with 14.765 people, and Turkmenistan citizens are ranked as the third with 10.642 people (General Directorate of Immigration Management, 2017). When the data are analyzed, it is observed that most of the international students in Turkey come from the related countries or the countries with historical or cultural ties with Turkey (Özoğlu, Gür and Coşkun, 2012). Although Turkey has developed rapidly in internationalization in education, it is still behind the OECD countries. While the number of international students in the OECD countries is 8% on average, it is at the level of 1.9% in Turkey (Şimşek and Bakır, 2016).

International education is an important tool for communities to remove their prejudices about people from different religions, countries and races and to develop an understanding and respectful point of view on different cultures. Mutual interaction and dialogue contribute to the change of stereotypes in mind. For example, in a study carried out on 11 students who came to the USA to receive education, it was observed that students' negative thoughts about Americans changed after they started to receive education (Pinkerton, 2006). Internationalization in education also provides sociological, political and economic resources for the countries accepting international students. In our country, there is a university in each province, and there are international students from different countries in each university. The citizens of many cities get the opportunity of interacting with foreign individuals and recognizing the cultures outside of their relatively closed cultures through international students. Turkey is a country where especially the students coming from the Turkish and related communities have a relatively easy adaptation due to the hospitality of people and its religious and cultural affinity. International students integrate with the city and have a mutual acculturation process by renting a house, doing shopping, working in different workplaces, meeting with their friends' family and neighbours. These students are also models to their friends in the class or dormitory with respect to receiving international education and increasing the motivation of their friends in benefiting from exchange programs. Some of the Turkish citizen students develop schemes to be international students thanks to these students or make positive or negative changes in existing schemes.

In the studies carried out on international students in our country, the issues on the communication experiences of students in the educational environment (Apaydın-Şen, 2008), their satisfaction levels (Bayraktaroğlu and Mustafayeva, 2010), their social support and social commitment (Traş and Güngör, 2011), their basic psychological needs (Yiğit, 2012), their social problems (Paksoy, Paksoy and Özçalıcı, 2012), their social adaptation (Özçetin, 2013), intercultural communication concerns of Turkish and foreign students participating in Erasmus program (Bozkaya and Erdem-Aydın, 2010), and their perceptions of Turkey and Turkish (Alyılmaz, Biçer and Çoban, 2015) were examined. Abroad, studies were carried out on the issues such as the stress sources of students (Chen, 1999), their satisfaction levels (Arambewela and Hall, 2009), their adaptation to anew culture (Evans and Stevenson, 2011), and student profiles, needs and problems (Ghanbary, 2017). No study aimed at determining the perceptions of international students studying in Turkey and university students of Turkish citizenship who continue their education in Turkey of being an international student, which is the subject of this study, was encountered. The idea that revealing the positive

and negative thoughts, stereotypes, worries and wrong information, if any, about being an international student by determining the perceptions of students who have and do not have this experience about being an international student will contribute to counselling studies to be performed and to the development of educational policies constitutes the reason for conducting this study.

In the study, an attempt to determine the students' perceptions of being an international student through metaphors was made. The metaphor is "to use a word or concept in a way that it will have different meanings other than what is accepted" (Turkish Language Society, 2015). Metaphors can be used to show how a concept or phenomenon is perceived (Aydın, 2011). Metaphors provide a libertarian environment that supports creative thinking, offers the opportunity to reveal different points of view, develops insight into learners, and entirely progresses according to the thinking system of individuals, not within the framework of certain limits (Zheng and Song, 2010; Koç, 2014). In the studies in which metaphor was used as a perception tool in Turkey, subjects such as the concept of teacher (Yılmaz, Göçen and Yılmaz, 2013), globalization (Kaya, 2013), book (Bektaş, Okur and Karadağ, 2014), environment (Meral, Küçük and Gedik, 2016), KPSS (public personnel selection examination) perceptions of students (Karadeniz, 2016) and perceptions of career (Korkut and Keskin, 2016) were studied.

The aim of this study was to determine the perceptions of international students studying in Turkey and university students of Turkish citizenship who continue their education in Turkey of being an international student through metaphors.

In line with this purpose, answers to the following questions were searched:

- By which metaphors do the international students studying in Turkey and university students of Turkish citizenship who continue their education in Turkey express the concept of "being an international student"?
- How do students describe the metaphors they have expressed?

2. Method

The model of the research, study group, collection and analysis of data are focused in this section.

2.1. Research model

This study, in which the metaphors attributed to being an international student by international students studying in Turkey and university students of Turkish citizenship who continue their education in Turkey were examined, was conducted according to the phenomenology model among the qualitative research designs. In the

phenomenology model, the personal experiences of participants are dealt with, and the perceptions of individuals and the meanings they attribute to events are examined (Baş and Akturan, 2013). In this study, the metaphor analysis was obtained by the fact that university students filled in the sentences given in the form of "being an international student is similar/like....., because.....".

2.2. Study group: Study group consisted of 79 students, 35 of whom were Turkish citizens and 44 of whom were international students, studying at Giresun University during the 2016-2017 spring semester. The demographic data of the students are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distributions of Students' Demographic Information

Variable Option		f%	
Student Type	International student	44	55.70
	Turkish citizen student	35	44.30
Gender	Female	37 (18U/19TC)	46.84
	Male	42 (26U/16TC)	53.16

As it is seen in Table 1, the study group consists of 37 female and 42 male students. 18 of female students are international students while 19 of them are Turkish citizen students. 26 of male students are international students while 16 of them are Turkish citizen students. The distribution of students according to the faculties where they study is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of Students According to the Faculties where They Study

International Students		Turkish citizen students	
Faculty	Number of Students	Faculty	Number of Students
Faculty of Education	20	Faculty of Education	18
FEAS	13	FEAS	12
Faculty of Engineering	11	Faculty of Engineering	5

The numbers of international students studying in the faculty of education, in the FEAS and in the faculty of engineering are 20, 13 and 11, respectively. 18 of the Turkish citizen students are studying in the faculty of education, 12 of them are studying in the FEAS, and 5 of them are studying in the faculty of engineering.

The reason for the selection of international students, who constituted the study group, from the three mentioned faculties is that most of the international students are

studying in these three faculties. The sample selection for Turkish students was performed based on typical case sampling, one of the types of purposeful sampling. In the selection of typical cases, opinions are generally received from individuals who have information on this subject (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013). The reason for the selection of Turkish students from the specified faculties is the idea that they have observations about being an international student as they are studying with international students and thus they will be able to develop metaphors more easily. The countries from where international students come are indicated in Table 3.

Table 3: Countries and Genders of International Students

Country	Total Number of Students/Gender
Azerbaijan	20 (13M/7F)
Uzbekistan	8 (4M/4F)
Turkmenistan	8 (5M/3F)
Kirghizstan	5 (2M/3F)
Kazakhstan	3 (2M/1F)
Total: 44(26M/18F)	

20 of international students are Azerbaijani citizens (13M/7F), 8 of them are Uzbekistani citizens (4M/4F), 8 of them are Turkmenistani citizens (5M/3F), 5 of them are Kirghizstani citizens (2M/3F), and 3 of them are Kazakhstani citizens (2M/1F). 26 of 44 international students are male students, and 18 of them are female students.

2.3. Collection of Data

The perceptions of university students of being international students were qualitatively collected through the metaphors. After the forms that were required to fill out were distributed to the students, the concept of metaphor was explained, and the examples of metaphors related to different concepts were shared. The students were given 15 minutes to fill out the forms, but it was observed that many students completed the form within the first 6-7 minutes.

2.4. Analysis of Data

The content analysis method was used in the analysis of data. The main reason for the use of content analysis in the study was to reach the concepts and relations that could explain the data collected. To achieve this purpose, the data are firstly conceptualized, then the data are logically organized according to the resulting concepts, and the themes describing the data are determined accordingly (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013). Four stages consisting of coding of data, creating categories, performing studies aimed

at ensuring validity and reliability, and the interpretation of findings were used in the analysis of data.

a) Coding of Data: At this stage, a metaphor table was created by determining the metaphors that the students created about being international students. By receiving the opinions of two faculty members whose field is educational sciences, the forms of 13 students were excluded from the scope of the study because the reason of the metaphor was not explained clearly.

b) Creating Categories: At this stage, the metaphors used by students to describe the concept of "being an international student" were grouped according to their common characteristics. While creating the categories, some metaphors were evaluated in several different categories according to their reasons (for example, the bird metaphor was evaluated in four different categories). In the study, the metaphors created by international students were included in 11 categories, and the metaphors created by the students from the Republic of Turkey were included in nine categories.

c) Studies Aimed at Ensuring Validity and Reliability: The facts should be observed and obtained as unbiased as possible to ensure validity in qualitative studies (Kirk & Miller, 1986; cited by Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013). For this reason, a guiding example was given to students to help them create metaphors. Moreover, since the obtained data should be reported in detail in ensuring the validity and how the researcher has reached the results should be clearly presented (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013), the steps followed were indicated in detail.

To ensure reliability, the relevant categories were firstly created by the researcher, and then the opinions of two faculty members whose field is educational sciences were received. So, the relevant categories were first given to the experts, and they were asked to point out whether each metaphor should be eliminated, into which category the metaphor falls, or whether a new categorization is needed. In the calculation of reliability, Miles and Huberman's (1994) formula " $Reliability = \frac{Consensus}{Consensus + Dissensus} \times 100$ " was taken as a basis. As a result of the calculations made, the reliability of the study was found to be 93%. This result is consistent with Saban's (2008) opinion that the desired reliability coefficient should be at least 90%.

3. Findings

International students in the study group produced 43 different valid metaphors while Turkish students produced 27 different valid metaphors. The metaphors created by the students are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Metaphors created by the International Students and Turkish Students in relation to being an international student

Metaphors created by the International Students	Metaphors created by the Turkish Citizen Students
To have 2-0 head start on life(1), Chorus in the song (1), Advantage (1), Difference (1), Chosen person (1), Hero (1), Bright red tea (1), Colored t-shirt (1), Chance for the one who could not get into the desired department (1), Diamond (1), Opportunity (1), Rainbow (1), Multichannel television (1), Tasting different dishes (1), Recognizing different cultures (1), Interacting with different cultures (1), Bird (2), Waterfall (1), River (1), Culture (1), Introducing the culture in another country (2), Flower (1), Multiplication table (1), Increasing the level in a computer game (1), Mountain (1), Adaptation (1), Phone Update (1), Taking responsibility on your own without your family (1), World (1), Freedom (1), Diving into ocean by getting out of the pool (1), A fish out of water (1), Shadow (1), Scorpion (1), Headache (1), Nature of Giresun (1), Transition to a higher-quality phone (1), Better (quality) education (3), Computer game (1), Awakening from sleep (1), Finding the truth (1), Seeing the real face of life (1), Seeing the life behind the stage (1)	Dream (1), Being a big fish in a small lake (1), Transition from one universe to another universe (1), Traveler (1), The world (3), Citizen of the world (2), Mermaid in the ocean (1), Wind (1), Caravan (1), Sun (1), Paper (1), Immigrant (1), Tree (1), Sea (2), Maroon beret (1), Chameleon (1), Iron (1), Rainbow (1), Bird (5), Music (1), Colorfulness of butterfly wings, (1) Sky (1), Loneliness in the crowd (1), Playing away a game (1), Adventure (1), Minority (1), Acculturation (1)

59 of 70 metaphors created indicated a positive judgment, and 11 of them indicated a negative judgment. In the study, the metaphors created by the international students were included in 11 categories, and the metaphors created by the students from the Republic of Turkey were included in nine categories. The categories into which the metaphors created by the students fell are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Categories in which the metaphors are included

Metaphor Categories of the International Students	Metaphor Categories of the Turkish Citizen Students
Category of Providing Privilege (Adding Value)	Category of Providing Privilege (Adding Value)
Category of Recognizing New Cultures	Category of Recognizing New Cultures
Category of Seeing New Countries (Places)	Category of Seeing New Countries (Places)
Category of Introducing Your Own Culture	Category of Introducing Your Own Culture
Category of Contributing to Development (Learning More)	Category of Contributing to Development (Learning More)
Category of Developing the Coping Skills	Category of Developing the Coping Skills

(overcoming the difficulties)	(overcoming the difficulties)
Category of Being a Citizen of the World	Category of Being a Citizen of the World
Category of Providing Freedom	Category of Providing Freedom
Category of Negative Perceptions	Category of Negative Perceptions
Category of Getting a Better Education	
Category of Recognizing the Life	

The category of providing privilege (adding value), the category of recognizing different cultures, the category of seeing new countries (places), the category of introducing your own culture (representing the country), the category of contributing to development (learning more), the category of developing the coping skills (overcoming the difficulties), the category of being a citizen of the world, the category of providing freedom, and the category of negative metaphors were created by both the international and Turkish citizen students, and the category of getting a better education and the category of recognizing the life were created only by the international students.

3.1 Category of Providing Privilege (Adding Value)

Metaphors included in this category are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Metaphors included in the Category of Providing Privilege (Adding Value)

International Students		Turkish Citizen Students	
Metaphor	Frequency	Metaphor	Frequency
To have 2-0 head start on life	1	Dream	1
Chorus in the song	1	Being a big fish in a small lake	1
Advantage	1		
Difference	1		
Chosen person	1		
Hero	1		
Bright red tea	1		
Colored t-shirt	1		
Chance for the one who could not get into the desired department	1		
Diamond	1		
Opportunity	1		
Total Number of Metaphors: 11		Total Number of Metaphors: 2	
		General Total: 13	

11 of a total of 13 metaphors that were included in the category of providing privilege (adding value) were produced by the international students, and 2 of them were produced by the Turkish citizen students. It is observed that the perceptions regarding the fact that to be an international student provides students with certain privileges and

makes them more valuable are included in the metaphors in this category. These perceptions are more evident, especially in international students. Some of the opinions attributed to metaphors are as follows:

UÖ: *"It is like an opportunity because everyone is not granted with it (M5), It is like an advantage because you have 2-0 head start on life (M11), It is like being a chosen person because you will get attention as you will have received education abroad in the future (M14), It is like a bright red tea because it is the most precious (M19)."*

TC: *"It is like being a big fish in a small lake because it is more competent and has a wider accumulation wherever it exists, and it becomes evident everywhere (F9), It is like a dream because it is a privilege, it's special, and it makes oneself feel different (F11)."*

3.2 Category of Recognizing New Cultures

Metaphors included in this category are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Metaphors included in the Category of Recognizing New Cultures

International Students		Turkish Citizen Students	
Metaphor	Frequency	Metaphor	Frequency
Rainbow	1	Transition from one universe	
Multichannel television	1	to another universe	1
Tasting different dishes	1		
Recognizing different cultures	1		
Interacting with different cultures	1		
Total Number of Metaphors: 5		Total Number of Metaphors: 1	
		General Total: 6	

5 of a total of 6 metaphors that were included in the category of recognizing different cultures were produced by the international students, and 1 of them was produced by the Turkish citizen student. In the metaphors in this category, it is observed that there are perceptions that to be an international student provides an opportunity to recognize different cultures. Some of the opinions attributed to metaphors in this regard are as follows:

UÖ: *"It is like tasting different dishes because the differences are good, they are experience (M9), it is like a multichannel television because it contains various colors and cultures (M10), It is like interacting with different cultures because a different environment that a person never knows actually brings a lot to him/her (F13)."*

TC: *"It is like transition from one universe to another universe because you suddenly find yourself in another culture, civilization (M10)."*

3.3 Category of Seeing New Countries (Places)

Metaphors included in this category are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Metaphors included in the Category of Seeing New Countries (Places)

International Students		Turkish Citizen Students	
Metaphor	Frequency	Metaphor	Frequency
Bird	1	Bird	1
		Traveler	1
		World	1
		Citizen of the world	1
		Mermaid in the ocean	1
		Wind	1
Total Number of Metaphors: 1		Total Number of Metaphors: 5	
		General Total: 6	

1 of a total of 6 metaphors that were included in the category of seeing new countries (places) was produced by the international student, and 5 of them were produced by the Turkish citizen students. In the metaphors in this category, it is observed that there are perceptions that to be an international student provides an opportunity to see new countries (places). Some of the opinions attributed to metaphors in this regard are as follows:

UÖ: *"It is like a bird because it travels country-by-country (M12)."*

TC: *"It is like a bird because you get about and visit everywhere (F2), It is like a wind because it travels to different countries (F3), It is like being a mermaid in the ocean because it goes to the shores of many countries, and it can visit the whole world (F4)".*

3.4 Category of Introducing Your Own Culture (Representing the Country)

Metaphors included in this category are presented in Table 9.

Table 9: Metaphors included in the Category of Introducing Your Own Culture
(Representing the Country)

International Students		Turkish Citizen Students	
Metaphor	Frequency	Metaphor	Frequency
Waterfall	1	Caravan	1
River	1		
Culture	1		
Introducing the Culture in Another Country	2		
Total Number of Metaphors: 4		Total Number of Metaphors: 1	
		General Total: 5	

4 of a total of 5 metaphors that were included in the category of introducing your own culture (representing the country) were produced by the international students, and 1 of them was produced by the Turkish citizen student. In the metaphors in this category, it is observed that there are perceptions that to be an international student provides students with an opportunity to introduce their cultures (countries) in other countries. Some of the opinions attributed to metaphors in this regard are as follows:

UÖ: "It is like representing your own country beside other international students in the country where you are studying because you represent your own country in another state, and you introduce your customs, your meals, your clothes (M7), It is like a culture because it carries so many things with it to the place it goes (M2), It is like a waterfall because it brings a lot of things with it (M3), It is like representing the culture of a country among other students because a foreign citizen in a foreign state shows who and what the population of his/her country are (M16)."

TC: "It is like a caravan because it carries its own culture to the places it goes (F10)."

3.5 Category of Contributing to Development (Learning More): Metaphors included in this category are presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Metaphors included in the Category of Contributing to Development (Learning More)

International Students		Turkish Citizen Students	
Metaphor	Frequency	Metaphor	Frequency
Flower	1	Sun	1
Multiplication table	1	Paper	1
Increasing the level in a computer game	1	Immigrant	1
		Tree	1
Total Number of Metaphors: 3		Total Number of Metaphors: 4	
General Total: 7			

3 of a total of 7 metaphors that were included in the category of contributing to development (learning more) were produced by the international students, and 4 of them were produced by the Turkish citizen students. In the metaphors in this category, it is observed that there are perceptions that to be an international student contributes to the development of students, and thus they can learn more. Some of the opinions attributed to metaphors in this regard are as follows:

UÖ: "It is like a flower because it develops and grows as it gets the things that are useful from the soil, water and air (F3), It is like a multiplication table because your life will become easier as you learn, you can solve many things more easily (M29), It is like increasing the level

in a computer game because you go to a higher level as you succeed, you develop yourself as you succeed in the game (M31)."

TC: "It is like a tree because it develops and grows over time, and it becomes beautiful as it grows (M12), It is like a paper because to write and fill out the paper is just like improving ourselves, more information is available in more writing (F15), It is like immigrants because they know more as they see everywhere and everything (M3)."

3.6 Category of Developing the Coping Skills (overcoming the difficulties)

Metaphors included in this category are presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Metaphors included in the Category of Developing the Coping Skills
(overcoming the difficulties)

International Students		Turkish Citizen Students	
Metaphor	Frequency	Metaphor	Frequency
Mountain	1	Sea	1
Adaptation	1	Maroon beret	1
Phone Update	1	Chameleon	1
Taking responsibility on your own without your family	1	Iron	1
Total Number of Metaphors: 4		Total Number of Metaphors: 4	
General Total: 8			

4 of a total of 8 metaphors that were included in the category of developing the coping skills (overcoming the difficulties) were produced by the international students, and 4 of them were produced by the Turkish citizen students. In the metaphors in this category, it is observed that there are perceptions that to be an international student develops students' coping skills and increases their abilities to overcome the difficulties. Some of the opinions attributed to metaphors in this regard are as follows:

UÖ: "It is like updating the phone because you adapt to a totally different atmosphere, innovations over time (M4), It is taking responsibility on your own without your family in another country because you learn to stand on your own feet (F6), It is like a mountain because you can cross it unless you give up, no matter how high or rough it is (F9)."

TC: "It is like maroon berets because they should be able to withstand everything (M8), It is like a chameleon because it adapts to all environments (M11), It is like an iron because it is durable, not easy to bend, can overcome difficulties (M16)."

3.7 Category of Being a Citizen of the World

Metaphors included in this category are presented in Table 12.

Table 12: Metaphors included in the C ategory of Being a Citizen of the World

International Students		Turkish Citizen Students	
Metaphor	Frequency	Metaphor	Frequency
World	1	World	1
		Being a citizen of the world	2
		Rainbow	1
		Flying bird	1
		Music	1
		Colorfulness of butterfly wings	1
T otal Number of Metaphors: 1		Total Number of Metaphors: 6	
		General Total: 7	

1 of a total of 7 metaphors that were included in the category of being a citizen of the world was produced by the international student, and 6 of them were produced by the Turkish citizen students. In the metaphors in this category, it is observed that there are perceptions that to be an international student contributes to students' being a citizen of the world. Some of the opinions attributed to metaphors in this regard are as follows: UÖ: *"It is like the world, there is no nationality, religion and country discrimination, everything is alike, there is no difference, there is no prejudice (F11)."*

TC: *"It is like the world because you band together and become one with all people (F14), It is like the colorfulness of butterfly wings because it is colorful and full of life like the world, you do not belong to a single place but everywhere (F16), It is like a rainbow because you know and see all the colors of the world, you start to recognize the world, you become a citizen of the world (M5), It is like music, it is universal, you enjoy it even though you don't understand its language, you find something from yourself in each music (F5)."*

3.8 Category of Providing Freedom

Metaphors included in this category are presented in Table 13.

Table 13: Metaphors included in the Category of Providing Freedom

International Students		Turkish Citizen Students	
Metaphor	Frequency	Metaphor	Frequency
Bird	1	Sea	2
Freedom	1	Sky	1
Total Number of Metaphors: 2		Total Number of Metaphors: 2	
		General Total: 4	

2 of a total of 4 metaphors that were included in the category of providing freedom were produced by the international students, and 2 of them were produced by the Turkish citizen students. In the metaphors in this category, it is observed that there are

perceptions that to be an international student makes students free. Some of the pinions attributed to metaphors in this regard are as follows:

UÖ: *"It is like a bird because it chooses the route it will go (M26), It is like freedom because it is liberty, to do what you want, to live a life free from pressures (F7)."*

TC: *"It is like a sea because it gives people freedom (F1), it is like the sky because it makes a person free (F12)."*

3.9 Category of Negative Perceptions

Metaphors included in this category are presented in Table 14.

Table 14: Metaphors included in the Category of Negative Perceptions

International Students		Turkish Citizen Students	
Metaphor	Frequency	Metaphor	Frequency
Diving into ocean by getting out of the pool	1	Loneliness in the crowd	1
A fish out of water	1	Playing away a game	1
Shadow	1	Adventure	1
Scorpion	1	Minority	1
Headache	1	Acculturation	1
		Bird	4
Total Number of Metaphors: 5		Total Number of Metaphors: 6	
		General Total: 11	

5 of a total of 11 metaphors that were included in the category of negative perceptions were produced by the international students, and 6 of them were produced by the Turkish citizen students. The adventure, minority and acculturation metaphors were created by the same student. The metaphors of the bird separated from the mother, alone bird, the bird separated from its squeaker and the flying bird were generally evaluated within the bird metaphor. In the metaphors in this category, it is observed that there are perceptions that to be an international student contains some difficulties. Some of the opinions attributed to metaphors in this regard are as follows:

UÖ: *"It is like diving into ocean by getting out of the pool because you remain separated from the house, where you have stayed throughout your life, and find yourself in a completely different place (M1), It is like a headache because your responsibilities increase and I hate taking responsibilities (M20), It is like a headache, it bothers and afflicts the person (M30), It is like a scorpion, the decision you have taken sometimes damages you (F8)."*

TC: *"It is like migratory birds because you do not belong to a certain place, you are treated like a foreigner everywhere (F6), It looks like a bird separated from its squeaker because it is separated from its nest, so it feels distressed (F7), It's like loneliness in the crowd because it's*

different to tell your feelings to a foreigner compared to tell them to someone to whom you are related, no matter how hard you try (F8), It is like playing away a game because you are longing for your supporters (M19)."

3.10 Category of Getting a Better Education: Metaphors included in this category are presented in Table 15.

Table 15: Metaphors included in the Category of Getting a Better Education

International Students		Turkish Citizen Students	
Metaphor	Frequency	Metaphor	Frequency
Nature of Giresun	1		
Transition to a higher-quality phone	1		
Better (quality) education	3		
Computer game	1		
Total Number of Metaphors: 4		Total Number of Metaphors: 0	
		General Total: 4	

In this category, while the international students produced four metaphors, the Turkish Citizen Students did not produce any metaphor. It is observed that some international students think that they are receiving a better education in Turkey compared to the education they can get in their own countries. Some of the opinions attributed to metaphors in this regard are as follows:

UÖ: "It is like studying in Turkey with better opportunities because there is a more comfortable and better education system here (M6), It is like the nature of Giresun because there are nice education and good teachers (F1), It is like transition to a higher-quality phone because you are transferred from a more limited environment to an environment where there is a more comfortable, freer and better education (F10)."

3.11 Category of Recognizing the Life

Metaphors included in this category are presented in Table 16.

Table 16: Metaphors included in the Category of Recognizing the Life

International Students		Turkish Citizen Students	
Metaphor	Frequency	Metaphor	Frequency
Awaking from sleep	1		
Finding the truth	1		
Seeing the real face of life	1		
Seeing the life behind the stage	1		
Total Number of Metaphors: 4		Total Number of Metaphors: 0	
		General Total: 4	

In the category of recognizing the life, while the international students produced four metaphors, the Turkish Citizen Students did not produce any metaphor. In the metaphors in this category, it is observed that there are perceptions that to be an international student contributes to recognizing the life. Some of the opinions attributed to metaphors in this regard are as follows:

UÖ: "It is like seeing the real face of life because it becomes easier to recognize the life as you meet more people (M25), It is like awaking from sleep because you begin to see how different the life is, that different things may occur in life (M28), It is like seeing the life behind the stage because you see that life is more different than you think, you have totally new experiences (F15)."

4. Discussion, Conclusion and Suggestions

This study was carried out to determine the perceptions of international students studying in Turkey and university students of Turkish citizenship who continue their education in Turkey of being an international student through metaphors. At the end of the study, international students studying in Turkey produced 43 different valid metaphors while university students of Turkish citizenship who continue their education in Turkey produced 27 different valid metaphors. It was observed that 59 of the 70 metaphors created indicated a positive judgment, and 11 of them indicated a negative judgment. The metaphors created by the international students were gathered in 11 categories, and the metaphors created by the Turkish citizen students were gathered in nine categories. Nine categories were jointly created by both the international and Turkish citizen students, and two categories were developed only by the international students.

The perceptions that to be an international student provides students with a privilege in their lives (adds value to them), enables them to recognize different cultures and to see new countries (places) and thus allows them to introduce their own cultures in other countries, allows them to have a better education than the education in their own countries and they develop and learn more, and that their efforts to get used to being separated from their family and to adapt to new cultures develop their coping skills, prepare them for life, increase their freedom and make them a citizen of the world are the prominent findings of the study. In addition to positive perceptions stated for international education, the fact that there are negative perceptions such as separation from the family, feeling alone and adapting to new cultures is also among the findings of the study.

The phenomenon of being an international student is considered to be a privilege especially by the students who have had this experience, and students state that this situation adds value to them. The reasons such as the fact that international education brings prestige to individuals and provides more opportunities for the international professional career cause students to leave their countries and continue their education in another country (Zheng, 2010). In a study carried out by the Foundation for Political, Economic and Social Research (SETA) in 2012, it was determined that to receive higher education in Turkey gives prestige to students from some countries and thus facilitates finding jobs in their own countries, particularly in private companies, in effective positions (Özoğlu et al., 2012). The findings of the study carried out are in parallel with the results of the SETA's research results.

In the study, perceptions that to be an international student provides opportunities to recognize different cultures, see new countries (places) and introduce your own culture (country) were determined. International student circulation increases mutual understanding, cooperation and solidarity between the countries and cultures (Özoğlu et al., 2012). To provide mutual cultural transmission among students and the promotion of these opportunities are important for higher education to gain an international identity (Urban and Palmer, 2014). A project aimed at further developing the relations between the Central Asian countries and spreading the Turkish culture in the Central Asian region (Great Student Project) was launched by the State of the Republic of Turkey in 1992-1993 (Ahmetbeyoğlu, 2007). The results of the study carried out are partially consistent with the expected results of this project. In the study carried out by Paksoy et al. (2012), it was determined that international students studying at the universities in the GAP (Southeastern Anatolia Project) Region would recommend their peers to get an education in Turkey when they returned to their own countries. This situation shows that students are generally pleased to be in Turkey and receive higher education. In a study carried out by Özer (2012), it was determined that international students were generally satisfied with Turkey, but some of the students had problems arising from cultural differences. In the study carried out in Kırklareli and Trakya Universities, students stated that the university where they studied met their academic expectations (Özkan and Acar-Güvendir, 2015). The mentioned research results are parallel with the perceptions that to be an international student contributes to the development of individuals and thus they can learn more, that were revealed in this study. New experiences such as different cultures, lifestyles, viewpoints, education systems, methodology and the use of technology in education contribute to the development of students.

To study in a country far away from one's family and from the culture in which a person was born and grown up contributes to the development of coping skills and adaptive skills of students. Students should be able to meet the expectations to be able to take their place in the adult world and to grow to maturity demanded by the adult world (Yörükoğlu, 2007). University students should have knowledge, understanding and skill that will develop their well-being and learn to stand on their feet (Doğan, 2006; Kır, 2007). While international students are adapting to a new culture, they take on more responsibilities compared to other students to be able to cope with the difficulties and adapt as the students who are away from their usual social support systems and a majority of which have language problems. These students try to cope with the problems such as cultural, economic, language and housing problems and also to show academic success at a certain level in a different education system. Therefore, it can be considered that overcoming difficulties and having successful experiences contribute to the development of these students' sense of responsibility and self-confidence.

Despite all of its positive aspects, there are also students who have problems such as the inability to adapt to new cultures, fulfilling the longing for family and feeling lonely during the international education. The fact that students have language problems further increases their adaptation problems (Tutkun, 2006; Karaoğlu, 2007; Çöllü and Öztürk, 2009; Güllü, 2010). In the study carried out by Kiroğlu et al. (2010), it was determined that almost all international students felt longing for their homes and missed their families, friends and homeland. The fact that students adequately benefit from the surrounding social support resources may facilitate social adaptation (Wintre and Bowers, 2007). For this reason, it is necessary to increase the interactions with other students by means of social activities for students to gain confidence and adapt (Telbis, Helgeson and Kingsbury, 2014). International students ask their universities to prepare orientation programs to overcome adaptation problems (Lijuan, 2002). In a study carried out by Nasrin (2001), international students stated that the preparation of discussion forums by the universities where they study could help them in the adaptation phase not to be exposed to discrimination, to remove the stereotypes, to introduce themselves better and to ensure that their classmates and instructors better understand their problems.

At the end of the study, the following suggestions were developed:

1. The experience of being an international student can make so many contributions to students with this experience, as it can be understood from the students' opinions. Therefore, it is possible to ensure that more students have such experiences with the practices such as undergraduate or postgraduate education, exchange programs or language training abroad.

2. Students state that they are introducing their own cultures (countries) by studying in different countries. Through international education, both international students and the individuals in the countries where they study know each other better by interacting with each other and can remove the stereotypes in their minds. This can be thought to contribute to the development of friendships between countries and the world peace. Therefore, it can be suggested to increase the interactions between students with the services, such as sports, arts, travel, cultural orientation programs and joint project studies.
3. Universities can contribute to the development of students' coping skills by providing orientation studies and psychological counselling services through their medico-social services, international student offices and student academic advisors. An orientation program can also be applied to the friends of these students in classrooms where they will study. The adaptation process of students can be facilitated through the peer counselling system.
4. In the report issued by the SETA in 2012, it was stated that the educational opportunities offered in Turkey could not be adequately and effectively introduced and this situation was one of the most important short comings of Turkey within the context of international student policy. Therefore, it is possible to focus on promotional activities, increase the number of promotion offices in foreign countries, and universities can participate in international higher education fairs abroad more.

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Levent Yayci
UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' PERCEPTION OF BEING AN INTERNATIONAL STUDENT:
A METAPHOR ANALYSIS STUDY

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